

Analysing the Performance of Electricity Generation through PV Rooftop Systems in Food Industry Facilities

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Abstract.

In recent years, photovoltaic (PV) systems show remarkable growth, contributing significantly to the global energy mix. This expansion encompasses diverse installations, from small residential to large industrial facilities, presenting challenges for efficient operation and maintenance (O&M). Despite the growing awareness of O&M's importance, there remains a misconception about its scope. This study emphasizes real-world application challenges of rooftop PV systems within the food industry. Parameters such as irradiance, module temperature, and power input and outputs of the inverters are monitored and analyzed to assess system performance. The study addresses different aspects for improvement in standard metrics and provides practical considerations. Focusing on three industries in the south of Spain, each equipped with rooftop PV self-consumption systems on their rooftops with nominal PV system powers ranging from 13.95 kW to 44.1 kW, the results show different operational scenarios with performance ratios (PRs) have ranged from 0.38 to 0.92. The findings underline the importance of considering user-defined requirements, grid distributor influences, and continuous advancements for analysing and evaluating PV system performance.

Keywords: System Performance, Rooftop Solar Photovoltaic systems.

1 Introduction and objectives

In recent years, the generation of electricity through photovoltaic (PV) systems has experienced significant expansion, making a noteworthy contribution to the energy mix in countries such as Spain, the United States, Germany, and China. Globally, installed PV capacity has experienced exponential growth, surging from 104 GW in 2012 to

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1581 GW in 2023 [1,2]. This increase in capacity has occurred not only in large facilities but also in small installations, potentially with a capacity of less than 100 kW. In Spain, the representative residential PV facility in 2023 is a 4.7 kW installation without storage [3]. Over one hundred and ten thousand PV rooftop systems were installed, equivalent to 527 MW. Concerning rooftop PV in industrial facilities, the average nominal power was 91 kW, surpassing fifteen thousand rooftop PV systems to reach 1400 MW [3]. It is crucial to highlight that, while the average power figure may be illustrative of the national reality in residential self-consumption, industrial installations exhibit wide dispersion, ranging from small installations of 15 kW to several-megawatt installations [4]. This type of installation presents a current and future challenge for operation and maintenance (O&M) to ensure optimal electricity generation [5].

Managing PV system requires crucial implementation of O&M strategies to ensure reliability, energy efficiency, and secure plant operation throughout its lifecycle [6]. Despite the growing awareness of O&M's importance, many investors and end-users are unfamiliar with relevant concepts and best practices. This misconception often arises from the belief that O&M is limited to tasks like module cleaning and checking the plant status on manufacturer-provided monitoring portals. In reality, O&M involves daily activities such as preventive fault diagnosis, equipment response analysis, and the formulation of strategies based on real operational data, contributing significantly to long-term performance [7,8]. Moreover, some users and investors, lacking awareness of the importance of O&M, are not inclined to invest time in it, including monitoring systems and data collection, due to the belief that these entail a low additional cost with minimal economic returns for the plant. Assessing performance is not a trivial task, involving various factors where multiple requirements and uncertain conditions must be simultaneously considered. Consequently, managers of PV power plants require monitoring methodologies to assess the operation's quality throughout its lifecycle in terms of daily, monthly, or annual performance [9].

In line with this objective, the IEC 61724 standard [10] plays a crucial role, aiming to establish definitions and terms for addressing the monitoring and analysis of PV systems. It additionally defines a categorization for monitoring systems, taking into account their complexity and technical specifications. This standard defines the parameters to be measured (e.g., irradiance, temperature), as well as the sensors (type, precision, etc.), their installation (location, placement, etc.), recalibration requirements, maintenance, etc. The methodology for measurements, data processing, and the parameters to be calculated are also outlined. The primary goal of monitoring PV systems is to evaluate the performance of each system and detect potential faults. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of the system is required, involving subsystem analyses, to determine performance parameters and metrics such as yields or efficiencies, loss factors, performance ratios, and indices [11].

The main objective of this study is to apply current regulations to various PV rooftop systems in food industry facilities. While recognizing the importance of metrics proposed by the standard, the goal is to address their limitations by acknowledging potential omissions of factors that may influence energy production.

2 Description of PV Rooftop Systems in Food Industry Facilities

Table 1. Facilities used in the study, along with the technical specifications of the PV modules and inverters for the Rooftop PV systems.

		Technical specifications	
01# Location Andalusia, Spain		P_0	13.95 kW
		No. PV modules	31
02# Location Andalusia, Spain		Nominal PV module power	450
		No. Inverters	1
03# Location Andalusia, Spain		Inverter model	3P3-15KW-4G
		Inverter brand	Solis
02# Location Andalusia, Spain		P_0	44.10 kW
		No. PV modules	90
03# Location Andalusia, Spain		Nominal PV module power	490
		No. Inverters	1
03# Location Andalusia, Spain		Inverter model	40 KTL-M3
		Inverter brand	Huawei
03# Location Andalusia, Spain		P_0	37.24 kW
		No. PV modules	76
03# Location Andalusia, Spain		Nominal PV module power	490
		No. Inverters	1
03# Location Andalusia, Spain		Inverter model	36 KTL-M3
		Inverter brand	Huawei

Three industries in southern Spain have PV self-consumption systems on their rooftops, with nominal PV array powers (P_0) of 13.95 kW (01#), 44.1 kW (02#), and 37.24 kW (03#). Plant 01# is composed of 31 modules, which are faced south-east (Azimuth -20°) and 12° tilt angle. Meanwhile, plant 02# consists of 90 modules, which are divided into two groups of sub generators with different orientations. The modules have an east-west configuration (Azimuth $-90^\circ, 90^\circ$) and tilt angle of 10° . Therefore, half of the modules are oriented to the east, while the other half are oriented to the west. Finally plant 03# has 76 modules that faces south-east (Azimuth -20°) and tilt angle of 5° . Table 1 shows these Rooftop PV systems. The table also provides key technical specifications related to modules, generators, and inverters.

In plant 01#, ABB Power Analyzer M4M 20 Rogowski is used for accurate monitoring of electrical parameters and power quality analysis, while, Energy Meter EM340DIN, serves as a three-phase energy meter for active energy measurement in industrial applications. Three phase inverter Solis-3P15K-4G is used for this plant. Meanwhile, in Plants 02# and 03#, Janitza Energy Analyzer UMG 103-CBM is used for measuring electrical parameters, Huawei SUN2000 inverters with three-phase current, are used in both systems. These inverters feature an efficiency of 98.4%, with power ratings of 40 kW (02# P2) and 36 kW (03# P3). Each inverter has 8 available string inputs, distributed in pairs for the 4 Maximum Power Point Trackers (MPPTs). These MPPTs can operate within a voltage range of 200V to 1000V.

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Environmental parameters and module temperature in all plants are monitored through the Datasol MET Cell. This device allows acquisition of solar radiation, module temperature, and ambient temperature. The MET radiation measurement includes temperature compensation for the module and has a range from 0 to 1400 W/m².

All data obtained from system components are visualized and stored through a web server, enabling easy downloading for analysis or real-time monitoring.

3 Data and Methodology

The Rooftop PV Systems in the Food Industry Facilities have been monitored for months.

The electrical and environmental parameters of Plant 01# were monitored in both September 2022 and November 2023. Apart from the temporal difference between these two months, there is also a different inverter configuration in November 2023. During this month, the inverter is set up to prevent energy injection into the electrical grid at the connection point between the industry and the public distribution grid. This configuration aims to ensure that the power at the grid connection point remains in a consumer balance, provided there is internal consumption exceeding the tolerance of the measurement system. This tolerance is calculated as the sum of the power measurement equipment's accuracy classes and the transformer or current measurement probe class. In contrast, in September 2022, the inverter is not configured to prevent energy injection into the electrical grid.

Regarding Plant 02#, the electrical and environmental parameters were monitored in both September 2023 and November 2023. In these months, there is no different inverter configuration, and the setup to prevent energy injection into the electrical grid is not active. Moreover, there is a difference in the distribution of PV modules between the arrays connected to the different MPPT of the inverter. In September 2023, there was a different number of modules in series for each MPPT. The inverter consists of 4 MPPTs with two inputs each. The number of modules in each MPPT in September was as follows: [18-18], [9-0], [18-0], [13-13]. For example, MPPT 1 consists of two strings of 18 modules each, and so on. In November 2023, all arrays of the inverter had the same number of modules in series. The number of modules in each MPPT in November is as follows: [15-15], [15-0], [15-0], [15-15].

For Plant 03#, the electrical and environmental parameters were monitored in September 2023 and November 2023. In this installation, the configuration to prevent energy injection into the electrical grid is not active, and it has the same number of modules in series in all input branches of the inverter.

In these installations, both the electrical parameters of the direct current (DC) and alternating current (AC) parts, as well as the environmental parameters, have been monitored and recorded. The measured parameters are in-plane irradiance, G_i , PV module temperature, T_{mod} , DC array voltage, V_A , DC array current, I_A , DC array power, P_A , AC output voltage, V_{out} , AC output current, I_{out} , and AC output power, P_{out} . They have been measured by devices with specifications recommended by the IEC 61724 standard. The considered recording interval has been five minutes, which may be suitable for this type

of installations. This study focus on the calculation of parameters outlined in the international standard IEC 61724 [10].

The first step involves processing and validating data in accordance with the standard recommendations. Subsequently, calculated parameters and metrics are obtained as outlined by the standard for the PV system. The ensuing formulations, characterized by summations, integrate the temporal aspect, where τ_k signifies the duration of the k th recording interval within a given reporting period, τ . The symbol Σ_k represents the sum across all recording intervals within the reporting period. For example, τ can be a day, a month, or a year, and k can be 1, 15, or 60 minutes. It is essential to note that in formulas featuring the product of power quantities and the recording interval τ_k , the power should be stated in kilowatts (kW), and the recording interval in hours for the resulting energy to be expressed in kilowatt-hours (kWh).

The in-plane irradiation, denoted as H_i and measured in $[W/m^2]$ is determined by multiplying the summation of in-plane irradiance values G_k by the recording interval τ_k :

$$H_i = \sum_k G_k \times \tau_k \tag{1}$$

Where G_k represent the irradiance incident upon the front side of the inclined surface parallel to the plane of the modules in the PV array, also known as plane-of-array (POA) irradiance.

The energy output of the PV generator, represented as the DC output energy from the PV array, and expressed in [kWh], is calculated as follows:

$$E_A = \sum_k P_{A,k} \times \tau_k \tag{2}$$

The cumulative AC output energy [kWh] of the PV system at the inverter's output, denoted as E_{out} , is calculated based on the inverter's output power, P_{out} , considering the recording interval τ_k :

$$E_{out} = \sum_k P_{out,k} \times \tau_k \tag{3}$$

Yields represent the ratio between an energy quantity and the array power rating (P_0), serving as an indicator of the actual operational efficiency relative to the rated capacity. They are expressed in units of $kWh \cdot kW^{-1}$, where kWh in the numerator denotes energy production and kW in the denominator means the system power rating. Inherently, the ratio, being commensurate with hours, conveys the temporal proportionality required for the array to operate at P_0 , thereby generating the designated energy quantity observed throughout the reporting period.

The PV array energy yield (Y_A) is defined as the energy output per rated kilowatt of the installed PV array:

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$$Y_A = E_A / P_0 \quad (4)$$

Where:

P_0 : is the sum of the DC power outputs derived from all installed PV modules under standard test conditions (STC) at the power rating reference condition.

The final system yield denoted as Y_f , is the net energy output of the entire PV system per rated kilowatt of the installed PV array:

$$Y_f = E_{out} / P_0 \quad (5)$$

The reference yield (Y_r) for a PV system is calculated by dividing the total in-plane irradiation by the module's reference in-plane irradiance:

$$Y_r = H_i / G_{i,ref} \quad (6)$$

Where the reference in-plane irradiance, represented as $G_{i,ref}$ ($\text{kW}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) is the irradiance at which P_0 is defined, typically specified under STC.

The reference yield denotes the hours required for solar radiation to match the incident solar energy observed during the reporting period, assuming reference irradiance levels under STC. If the reporting period spans one day, Y_r effectively represents the equivalent number of sun hours at the reference irradiance per day.

Yield losses are determined by deducting yields. They are expressed in units of $\text{kWh}\cdot\text{kW}^{-1}$ (or h), they represent the duration for which the array would need to operate at its P_0 to compensate for the corresponding losses observed throughout the reporting period.

The array capture loss, denoted as L_c , encompasses losses attributed to the operational aspects of the array, such as losses in wiring and junction boxes before DC measurement, array temperature effects, soiling, etc. It is formally defined as:

$$L_c = Y_r - Y_A \quad (7)$$

The balance of systems (BOS) loss, denoted as L_{BOS} , quantifies the losses within the BOS components, encompassing the inverter, as well as all wiring and junction boxes not accounted for in the array capture loss. It is defined as:

$$L_{BOS} = Y_A - Y_f \quad (8)$$

The efficiency of the rated array is expressed as:

$$\eta_{A,0} = P_0 / (G_{i,ref} \times A_a) \quad (9)$$

In this context, the total array area (A_a) is calculated as the sum of the frontal surface areas of the PV modules, delineated by their outer boundaries.

The mean system efficiency throughout the reporting period is formally characterized by:

$$\eta_f = E_{out} / (H_i \times A_a) \tag{10}$$

The parameter η_{BOS} , representing the BOS efficiency throughout the reporting period, is a dimensionless value and is defined as:

$$\eta_{BOS} = E_{out} / E_A \tag{11}$$

The performance metrics defined in the standard are not mandatory, and their use may depend on the system design and user requirements. The most suitable metric for a specific application may vary. In this document, the performance ratio will be employed.

The Performance Ratio (PR) is defined as the coefficient between the Y_f and Y_r . It serves to quantify the comprehensive impact of output losses within the system, arising from factors such as array temperature, inefficiencies, and failures in system components. This includes considerations for system component balancing.:

$$PR = Y_f / Y_r \tag{12}$$

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 1 illustrates the normalized parameters of the Rooftop PV systems in the Food Industry Facilities. The left y-axis represents the DC power generated by the PV array (input to the inverter), $P_{A,k}$, and the AC power output, $P_{out,k}$, both parameters are normalized with P_0 . Meanwhile, the right y-axis represents the in plane irradiance, G_k , and it is normalized to $G_{i,ref}$.

The four subplots in Figure 1 correspond to Plant 01#, with subplots (a) and (b) representing parameters on September 4 2022, and November 1 2023, respectively. The difference between these plots is due to the inverter configuration, with (b) set to prevent energy injection into the grid. Plot (b) demonstrates a limitation in electricity generation as the PV system's energy output only meets the industry's electrical demands. Even on a clear day, the photovoltaic generator hardly surpasses 15% of its nominal capacity throughout the day. On the other hand, on September 4, 2022, another clear day, the PV system operated at almost full capacity. Both operating scenarios may be considered suitable as they align with user-defined requirements, and the inverter configuration may be influenced by the requirements of the grid distributor.

Additionally, Figure 1 includes plots (c) and (d) representing parameters of PV system 02# on September 24, 2023 and November 7, 2023, respectively. Between these dates, there was a change in the distribution of modules in series among arrays connected to different MPPTs of the inverter. While this change should not pose a problem within voltage design ranges, some MPPTs experience suboptimal operation due to module voltage ranges not aligning with optimal MPP window. This situation may be providing a non-optimal performance.

Table 2 and Figure 2 display the results for various parameters and metrics across the three installations over different months. Columns and figures (a) and (b) correspond to PV system 01# for the months of September 2022 and November 2023, respectively. Columns and figures (c) and (d) pertain to PV system 02# for the months of September 2023 and November 2023, respectively. Finally, columns and figures (e) and (f) relate to PV system 03# for the months of September 2023 and November 2023, respectively.

In Table 2, columns (a) and (b), despite being the same system, show a difference of more than 55% in the Performance Ratio. This discrepancy, in addition to occurring in different months (September and November), is primarily attributed to the behaviour of the inverter. In September, as previously indicated, the inverter attempts to track the maximum power point. In November, however, the inverter's goal is solely to meet the industrial load demand and prevent the injection of electrical energy into the grid. Since the capacity of the photovoltaic generator exceeds the industrial load demand in this installation, the inverter operates most of the time outside the maximum power point, resulting in higher capture losses and reducing the efficiency of the rated array by half. A 14% reduction in the balance-of-system efficiency is also observed when comparing September and November. Overall, there is a decrease in the η_f . Although this is not the most suitable from an energy criterion, it is a desired behavior by the system user and it may be a requirement from the electric utility due to potential transformer or distribution network congestion.

PV system 01# and PV system 03# have identical orientations and very similar inclinations, but they are situated in different locations of southern Spain. As shown in Table 2, H_i columns (b) and (e) is almost identical for the same month. However, since $\eta_{A,0}$ in PV system 01# is less than half, even though the inverters and modules are not exactly the same, it may be mainly attributed to the inverter configuration. Both Table 2 and Figure 2 indicate that for PV system 03#, the efficiencies and PR are relatively similar and high between both months. In this system, the PR values are always above 0.75.

On the other hand, the analysis results for PV system 02# show that configuring arrays with different numbers of modules in series, even in different Maximum Power Point Trackers of the same inverter, can reduce the system efficiency and PR. A better system performance was observed in November, following the reconfiguration, with an increase in PR from 0.7 to 0.85. Conversely, this behaviour is not observed in PV system 03#, where the PR remains nearly constant between the two months. While this behaviour could be influenced by other factors such as a reduction in the average module temperature or possible dirt accumulation, the primary cause is likely the reconfiguration of the modules.

Fig. 1. DC power generated by the photovoltaic array, the AC power at the output of the inverter, and the radiation in the incident plane a) PV system 01#; b) PV system 01#; c) PV system 02#; d) PV system 02#;

Table 2. Monthly calculated parameters and Metrics for the Installations.

Parameters	a	b	c	d	e	f
	PV system 01	PV system 01	PV system 02	PV system 02	PV system 03	PV system 03
	September 2022	November 2023	September 2023	November 2023	September 2023	November 2023
H_i (kWh/m ²)	173.94	94.44	168.22	80.69	165.34	94.43
E_A (kWh)	2096.60	584.90	5320.30	3088.40	5320.32	3297.40
E_{out} (kWh)	2086.80	499.12	5219.90	3028.20	5219.98	3238.30
Y_A kWh·kW ⁻¹ (or h)	150.29	41.93	120.64	70.03	142.87	88.54
Y_f kWh·kW ⁻¹ (or h)	149.59	35.78	118.37	68.67	140.17	86.96
Y_r kWh·kW ⁻¹ (or h)	173.94	94.44	168.22	80.69	165.34	94.43
L_c kWh·kW ⁻¹ (or h)	23.64	52.51	47.58	10.65	25.36	5.89
L_{BOS} kWh·kW ⁻¹ (or h)	0.71	6.15	2.28	1.36	2.69	1.59
$\eta_{A,0}$ (p.u)	0.18	0.09	0.15	0.18	0.18	0.19
η_f (p.u)	0.18	0.08	0.15	0.18	0.17	0.19
η_{BOS} (p.u)	0.99	0.85	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98
PR (p.u)	0.86	0.38	0.70	0.85	0.83	0.92

Fig. 2. Daily PR. a) PV system 01#; b) PV system 01#; c) PV system 02#; d) PV system 02#; e) PV system 03#; f) PV system 03#

5 Conclusion

The study underscores the significance of adapting standard metrics to real-world operational complexities in PV systems. The influence of inverter configurations and module distributions on system performance is evident, impacting energy generation and efficiency.

Performance indices based on ratings are relatively straightforward to calculate; however, these indices may overlook known factors that cause the system's energy production to deviate from expectations solely based on manufacturer-provided information. In the analysed installations, different PRs were found for different causes. The analysed monthly PR values vary from 0.38 to 0.92. It is worth mentioning that in PV system 01, due to a change in the inverter configuration, the system went from a PR of 0.86 in September 2022 to 0.38 in September 2023. On the other hand, in PV system 02, the PR improved from 0.7 to 0.85 from September to November by changing the distribution of the modules to ensure the maximum energy extraction range of the inverter. The findings emphasize the need for a determinate approach in assessing PV system performance, considering user preferences and grid distributor requirements. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of addressing these intricacies in monitoring and maintenance strategies.

The study contributes to bridging the gap between standards and practical challenges, providing insights for industry. Future research directions may explore advanced monitoring methodologies and adaptive strategies to enhance the overall reliability and performance of PV rooftop systems in industrial settings. As well as, extending the monitoring period to a full year or more to better capture seasonal variations and long-term performance trends. In addition, the focus will be broadened to include

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a wider range of industries and to analyse grid dependency in both grid-connected and off-grid scenarios.

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